

OCEAN:ICE News – January 2025

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Happy New Year!! We hope you had a lovely Christmas break!

Welcome to January's edition of OCEAN:ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN:ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, including articles on the American Geophysical Union (AGU) in Washington, a recent OCEAN:ICE Paper. We have upcoming Climate Coffees that you can register for in January and February. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in February!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Vio Coulon

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Vio Coulon, an Ice Sheet Modeller working as a Postdoc at the [ULB](#) in Brussels.

Read the feature on Vio [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

OCEAN:ICE at the American Geophysical Union (AGU).

OCEAN:ICE took part in the the American Geophysical Union (AGU) in Washington on 9-13th December.

[Mike Meredith \(BAS\)](#) gave an invited talk in the session “Antarctic Sea Ice and the Southern Ocean: Coupled Processes, Variability, and Change”, focussing on the role of glacial calving on ocean transformations and their impacts.

You can read the full article [here](#).

Strolling to the Convention Centre past the Washington Monument on a clear December day.

The queue to register required a hangar-sized room to itself on the Monday morning.

OCEAN:ICE Paper

Members from OCEAN:ICE recently published a paper on Future Freshwater Fluxes From the Antarctic Ice Sheet. The study, authored by a team of climate scientists, looks at the potential impact of ice melt on sea levels and climate systems over the coming centuries. Members from OCEAN:ICE include Written by Violaine Coulon, Jan De Rydt, Qing Qin, Frank Pattyn.

In the paper, results show that freshwater release from the Antarctic ice sheet into the Southern Ocean is projected to increase in the coming decades and centuries.

Read the article about the paper here: [OCEAN:ICE Paper – Future Freshwater Fluxes From the Antarctic Ice Sheet - OCEAN:ICE](#)

The image is a promotional graphic for a paper. It features a background of a blue sky over a snowy, icy landscape. In the top left corner, there is the OCEAN:ICE logo, which consists of a stylized globe icon followed by the text 'OCEAN:ICE'. Below the logo, the text 'OCEAN:ICE Paper Published:' is written in white. The main title, 'Future Freshwater Fluxes From the Antarctic Ice Sheet', is written in large, bold, white letters across the center. In the bottom left corner, there is a small European Union flag icon followed by the text: 'OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation'.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have two upcoming Climate Coffee events, make sure you register for both through the link on OCEAN:ICE.

Rachel Sanders on The dominance of biology in driving North Atlantic oxygen trends

Check the abstract: [The dominance of biology in driving North Atlantic oxygen trends Tickets, Thu, 23 Jan 2025 at 10.00 | Eventbrite](#)

23 January 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

23 January 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Rachel Sanders (UKRI-BAS)

**The dominance of biology in driving
North Atlantic oxygen trends**

Climate Coffee with Beatrice Maddalena Scotto on Multi-Model Framework for Tracking Pollutant Dispersion in the Mediterranean Sea

Check the abstract: [Climate coffee with Beatrice Scotto \(ETT\) Tickets, Thu, 20 Feb 2025 at 10.00 | Eventbrite](#)

20 February 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

20 February 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Beatrice Maddalena Scotto (ETT)

**Multi-Model Framework for Tracking
Pollutant Dispersion in the
Mediterranean Sea**

Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 27-30 January 2025, [Arctic Frontiers 2025: Beyond Borders](#), Tromsø, Norway & online
- 20-28 March 2025, [Arctic Science Summit Week \(ASSW\) 2025](#), Boulder, Colorado (USA)
- 27 April - 2 May 2025, [EGU General Assembly 2025](#), Vienna
- 9-13 June 2025, [United Nations Ocean Conference \(UNOC3\)](#), Nice
- 20-25 July 2025, [Busan IAMAS-IACS-IAPSO Joint Assembly 2025](#) (JMCP20), the Republic of Korea

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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